

Project: Visualized relationships - functions and problems. A repertoire-oriented investigation of visual and image-related communication among couples and friends in Switzerland. The project has been funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation, grant n°179484 ¹

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Short methodological description: Our methodology involved interviewing 60 individuals from 30 dyads, including 21 couples and 9 friendships, through a combination of pair and individual interviews, resulting in 90 interviews overall. These qualitative, semi-structured interviews included visual techniques such as network drawing and visual elicitation. To examine changes in visual communication during COVID-19, participants were re-contacted in follow-up video interviews after an initial quantitative survey assessing their well-being.

Participants Overview									
General information									
Participants	Gender	Age	Type & duration of relationship	Living situation	Pair interviews	Individual interviews	*Number of surveys	*Number of video calls	*Type of cases
G01 (Hannah & Timo)	F/M	18/18	Couple, 2 years	Living apart	1	1	2	1 (Hannah)	B
G02 (Cara & Mike)	F/M	37/54	Couple, 4 years, Cara has 1 child, Mike has 2 children	Living apart	1	1	2	1 (Mike)	B
I03 (Marika & Tommaso)	F/M	33/33	Married, 12 years, 2 children	Living together	1	1	2	0	B
I04 (Dennis & Valentina)	F/M	35/30	Married, 17 years, 2 children	Living together	1	1	0	0	B

¹ See <https://data.snf.ch/grants/grant/179484>

² Author names have been ordered alphabetically. All contributors have made equal and substantial contributions to this work.

F05 (Zoé & Lucas)	F/M	28/28	Couple, 2 years	Living together	1	1	1	0	B
F06 (Manon & Hugo)	F/M	32/31	Couple, 3.5 years	Living together	1	1	2	1 (Hugo)	B
I07 (Carolina & Matteo)	F/M	19/19	Couple, 3 years	Living apart (moved together during COVID-19)	1	1	2	2	B
I08 (Maurizio & Vanessa)	M/F	20/20	Friends, 7 years	Living apart	1	1	1 (Maurizio)	1 (Maurizio)	B
I09 (Derrick & Pietro)	M/M	25/25	Friends, 1.5 years	Living apart	1	1	1 (Derrick)	1 (Derrick)	B
I10 (Diego & Marianna)	M/F	32/31	Married, 6,5 years	Living together	1	1	0	0	A
G11 (Raul & Tobias)	M/M	24/22	Couple, 1.5 years	Living together	1	1	2	0	B
G12 (Lily & Nathan)	F/M	23/25	Couple, 7.5 years	Living together (living apart during COVID-19)	1	1	2	2	B
G13 (Fiona & Kim)	F/F	26/24	Couple, 1.5 years	Living apart	1	1	1 (Fiona)	0	IB
G14 (Anita & Gaby)	F/F	56/55	Friends, 36 years	Living apart	1	1	2	2	IB
G15 (Mario & Vincent)	M/M	52/47	Friends, 22 years	Living apart	1	1	2	1 (Vincent)	IB
G16 (Nathalie & Verena)	F/F	36/41	Friends, 16 years	Living apart	1	1	2	1 (Verena)	IB
G17 (Gloria & Martin)	F/M	69/69	Married (2 nd time), 14 years, Martin has 2 children	Living together	1	1	0	0	A
I18 (Adelaide & Nola)	F/F	20/20	Friends, 4 years	Living apart	1	1	0	0	A

F19 (Liesel & Fernand)	F/M	80/91	Married, 50 years	Living together	1	1	0	0	A
F20 (Jade & Loic)	F/M	51/50	Friends, 6 years	Living apart	1	1	0	0	A
F21 (Urs & René)	M/M	55/53	Friends, 30 years	Living apart	1	1	0	0	A
F22 (Madeleine & Pierre)	F/M	62/61	Married, 32 years, 2 children	Living together	1	1	0	0	A
I23 (Natalia & Patricia)	F/F	29/40	Married, 3 years	Living together	1	1	0	0	A
I24 (Costanza & Alberto)	F/M	25/25	Couple, 3,5 years	Living together	1	1	0	0	A
I25 (Dreina & Leonardo)	F/M	22/22	Couple, 2,5 years	Living together	1	1	0	0	A
I26 (Filiberto & Chiara)	M/F	23/21	Couple, 5 years	Living apart	1	1	0	0	A
I27 (Giuseppina & Silvestro)	F/M	35/36	Couple, 9 years	Living together	1	1	0	0	A
I28 (Lisandra & Walter)	F/M	58/65	Open relationship, 9 years, both have children	Living together	1	1	0	0	A
I29 (Giorgia & Yara)	F/F	26/25	Friends, 10 years	Living apart	1	1	0	0	A
I30 (Alessandro & Ivan)	M/M	35/36	Couple, 5 years, Alessandro has 1 child	Living together	1	1	0	0	A

Note. All participants' names are anonymized. The couple ID gives information about the language of the interviews; G=German; I=Italian; F=French. Relationship duration is based on participants' assessment. All participants were interviewed in a pair interview and a subsequent individual interview (see project description).

*COVID-19 interrupted data collection. Thus, we have B="before"-cases (i.e., all interviews conducted before the emergence of COVID-19), IB="in-between"-cases (i.e., a part of the interviews conducted before the emergence of COVID-19, the other part after the first wave of COVID-19 in Switzerland), and A="after" cases (i.e., all interviews conducted after the first wave of COVID-19). For A="after"-cases, there is no survey or video-interview data.